

Assessment of Graduates of College of Agriculture of Laguna States Polytechnic University 2015-2019

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Abstract:- This tracer study was conducted to determine the assessment of Laguna State Polytechnic University, College of Agriculture graduates from 2015-2019, this study employed descriptive method of research design to collect data, the researcher adopted a survey questionnaire adopted from the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). The survey revealed that the majority respondents of this study are single, 21-23 of age. They were generally graduate in 2017, most of them do not pursuing graduate studies. Majority of graduates are gainfully employed with frequency of 283 or 74.27%, 75 or 19.78% of them were not employed because they have lack of work experience, have no job opportunity. 132 or 46.64% are satisfied with their current job, most of them are receiving a gross monthly salary of range Php5,001-10,000, salaries, benefits and the proximity to residence are the reason why they accept their current job. 102 or 36.04% have Professional, technical or supervisory positions, majority of the have Contractual and job Order status of appointment and only 40 or 14.13% are regular employee. The results of the study confirm the findings of several studies that the challenge to job seekers include the lack of skills, graduates' preparation is lacking or not enough and preferences or qualifications of companies. This study resulted to the recommendation to strengthen the alumni placement program, the colleges may sustain and improved facilities for the field and hands-on activities of the students and the University may consider additional faculty in the field of soil science, and agricultural economics.

Keywords:- *alumni, assessment, college of agriculture, graduates, , tracer study*

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is very important part of our lives. It is also a manifestation of quality. Education is a process and a product. As a process, education is a system whereby an individual acquires knowledge, skills and attitudes that are essential in attaining an objective or set of objectives and have a good life.

Graduate tracer study is a survey of graduates from education institutions, which takes place sometime after graduation or at the end of the training. A study of Dato et.al. (2006) cited that Graduate Tracer Study has proven to be an effective method in getting accurate and quick inputs for the purpose of ensuring the human capital produced by higher education institutions are always relevant and be able to meet the ever-changing demand of job market.

Higher Education is universally recognized as a fundamental building block for human development (Buama 2018).

Laguna State Polytechnic University, College of Agriculture has been established to produced graduates with high quality general manpower equipped with necessary skills right knowledge and attitudes in the various fields of Agricultural entrepreneurship, Agricultural education and business management and to train trainers in its area of distinctive competence to effectively respond to the increasing demands, challenges and opportunities for global competitiveness. The alumni are considered as the best evidence of a program's effectiveness in terms of employment and positions held. Moreover, they are a good source of feedback regarding the program's relevance in the current labor market.

The purpose of this study is to determine the performance of Laguna States Polytechnic University, College of Agriculture graduates as basis for curriculum enhancement.

This study generally aimed to determine the assessment of Laguna State Polytechnic University, College of Agriculture graduates from 2015-2019.

Specific Objectives:

- To determine the profile of the graduates in terms of:
 - Age
 - Civil status
 - gender
 - year graduated
 - Pursuing graduate studies
 - Reason why pursuing graduate studies
- To determine the employability status of the graduated in terms of:
 - employment status
 - reason why not yet employed
 - job satisfaction
 - monthly salary
 - relevant to the degree program
 - Reason for accepting the job
 - Employment position
- To list down problem encountered of graduate in looking for a job.
- To solicit suggestion, comments and advises, from the respondents regarding their job experience.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This researcher employeddescriptive method of research design to collect data Graduates of College of Agriculture under Bachelor of Science in Agriculture (BSA), Bachelor of Science in Agricultural Education (BSAgEd), Bachelor of Science in Agribusiness (BSAb) and Bachelor in Agricultural

Technology (BAT), the researcher adopted a survey questionnaire adopted from the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), which used in similar study.

The respondents of the study are graduates of Laguna State Polytechnic University College of Agriculture from 2015 to 2019. The questionnaire was organized and customized to according to the purpose of the study. The researcher utilized 381 graduates as respondents of this study, In person distribution, electronic questionnaires, social media via Facebook messaging and telephone was used to collect data. The frequency and the percentage were presented in tabular form.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Profile of the Graduates

Table 1 shows that in the distribution of respondents in terms of age. Majority of the respondents with the frequency

of 186 or 48.82% are range from 21-23 years old, 111 or 29.13% are range in 18 to 20 years old, while 36 or 9.55% are range in 24-26 years old. 23 or 6.14% are range in 27 to 29 years of age, 18 or 4.73% are 30 to 33 years old and only 6 or 1.57% are 34 years old and above

. According to Buama (2014) cited in De Guzman (2007), in the workplace, professionalism is expected. The problem is that even after college, the person is still not prepared to work. Many employees are too immature, they cannot even pass interviews. So, it ended up with countless numbers of jobless all waiting in vain for that little luck in looking for a job. On the other hand, older people experience most age discrimination. However, it also takes place against young people. It is now unlawful for an employer to impose a lower age limit when recruiting, unless this age restriction can be objectively justified or is imposed by law.

Age	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
18-20	111	29.13	1
21-23	186	48.82	2
24-26	36	9.55	3
27-29	23	6.14	4
30-33	18	4.73	5
34 and above	6	1.57	6
Total	381	100	

Table 1: Profile of the respondents in terms of age.

Table 2 shows most of the respondents are single with a frequency of 190 or 49.87%, 137 or 35.96% are married and respondent that are separated, divorced, widow or widower have frequency of 3 or 0.78% respectively.

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Single	190	49.87	1
Married	137	35.96	2
Single parent born a child but not married	13	3.42	5
Married but not living with spouse	14	3.	4
Separated/Divorced	3	0.78	6
Widow or widower	3	0.78	7
No response	21	5.51	3
Total	381	100	

Table 2: Profile of the respondents in terms of civil status.

Table 3 revealed that majority of the graduates-respondents are female with a frequency of 221 or 58% of the total respondents and 160 or 42% are male. This result indicates that the College of Agriculture graduates are dominated by female.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Male	160	42	2
Female	221	58	1
Total	381	100	

Table 3: Profile of the respondents in terms of gender.

Table 4 shows the profile of the graduate-respondent in terms of year they were graduated it revealed that 111 or 29.13% graduated on 2017, 95 or 24.94% obtained their degree in 2018, 83 or 21.78% finished their studies on 2016 and 66 or 17.32% are graduated of 2019, while the remaining only 26 or 6.82% of the total respondents received their diploma in 2015.

Year Graduated	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
2015	26	6.82	5
2016	83	21.78	3
2017	111	29.13	1

2018	95	24.94	2
2019	66	17.32	4
Total	381	100	

Table 4: Profile of respondents in term of year graduated

Table 5 revealed that majority of the graduates from the college of Agriculture did not pursue graduate studies with 192 or 50.39%, while only 21 or 5.52% are pursuing their graduate studies.

Pursuing Graduate Studies	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Yes	21	5.52	3
No	192	50.39	1
No Response	168	44.09	2
Total	381	100	

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Table 5: Pursuing Graduate Studies

Table 6 shows the reason why the graduates-respondents pursue their graduate studies, 9 or 42.86 pursuing in graduate studies for promotion and 7 or 33.33% states that they continue to pursue their graduate studies for professional growth.

Reasons	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
For promotion	9	42.86	1
For professional development	7	33.33	2
To gain new knowledge and skills	1	4.62	4.5
Influence of colleagues	1	4.62	4.5
No Response	3	14.47	3
Total	21	100	

Table 6: Reason of pursuing graduate studies

B. Employment Status

Table 7 revealed that majority of graduates are gainfully employed with frequency of 283 or 74.27%, while unemployed has 75 or 19.68%. The statistics and scenarios of unemployment and underemployment are unsurprising (Cooper, 2018) because graduates develop and expand the skills for better jobs later. However, Porter (2012) stressed that most of the college graduates struggle in finding jobs due to a lack of practical and professional skills.

Employed	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Yes	283	74.27	1
No	75	19.68	2
No Response	23	6.04	3
Total	381	100	

Table 7: Employment Data in Terms of Employment

Table 8 shows the reasons why the respondents graduates are not yet employed 15 or 20% have lack of work experience, 12 or 16% have no job opportunity, while only 1 or 1.33% are not yet employed because of the family concern and not to find a job.

According to Lina (2019), after graduation is the time where fresh graduates confront with the realities beyond the academic world and become an active job seeker but will face the harsh statistics that only 35 to 40% will land a job and barely 10% will start a career related to the degree earned and the rest will join the unemployed status.

Reason	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Advanced for further study	5	6.67	7
Health related reason	9	12.00	5
Lack of work experience	15	20.00	1
No job opportunity	12	16.00	3
Did not look for a job	11	14.67	4
Running own business	8	10.66	6
Family concern and not to find a job	1	1.33	8

No Response	14	18.67	2
Total	75	100	

Table 8: Reasons why the respondents graduates are not yet employed

Table 9 employ-ability status in terms of Satisfaction on the current job majority 132 or 46.64% are satisfied with their current job,81 or 28.62% stated that they much appreciated their job, while only 8 or 2.84% are not satisfied with their current job.

Satisfaction	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Very much appreciated	39	13.78	3
Much appreciated	81	28.62	2
Satisfied	132	46.64	1
A little satisfied	7	2.47	6
Not satisfied	8	2.84	5
No Response	16	5.65	4
Total	283	100	

Table 9: Satisfaction on the current job

Table 10 shows the employment status of respondents in terms of monthly salary in their previous job. 145 or 38.06% are receiving a gross monthly salary of range Php5,001-10,000 from their previous job,92 or 24.15% are receiving Php5,000 and below, while 1 or 0.26% is receiving Php25,001-30,000 and 37 or 9.71% have no response.

Monthly Salary	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
5,000 and below	92	24.15	2
5,001-10,000	145	38.06	1
10,001-15,000	87	22.84	3
15,001-20,000	15	3.93	5
20,001-25,000	4	1.05	6
25,001-30,000	1	0.26	7
No Response	37	9.71	4
Total	381	100	

Table 10: Employment Data in Term of Monthly Salary

Table 11 employ-ability status in terms of relevant to the degree program it shows that 125 or 44.17% are in agriculture related job and 121 or 13.07% have a job that are not related in agriculture.

employment generated by agriculture, forestry and fishing establishments with 20 or more employees reached 145,237 in 2015. Of the total workforce, 143,732 workers, or 99 percent, were paid employees while the remaining 1 percent were working owners and unpaid workers.

According to the survey in 2015 of Aranda (2018); and to date are in the agriculture, forestry and fishing. The total

Relevant to the degree program	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Agriculture related	125	44.17	1
Not agriculture related	121	42.76	2
No Response	37	13.07	3
Total	283	100	

Table 11: relevant to the degree program

Table 12 shows the employ-ability of respondents in terms of what are the reasons for accepting the job, it revealed that most of the respondent reason are the salaries and benefits with a frequency of 115 or 40.64%, followed by the proximity to residence with 83 or 29.33%, career challenges with 42 or 14.84%, while related to special skills have a frequency of 35 or 12.37%

Reason	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Salaries and benefits	115	40.64	1
Career challenges	42	14.84	3
Related to special skills	35	12.37	4
Proximity to residence	83	29.33	2
No Response	8	2.82	5
Total	283	100	

Table 12: Reason for accepting the job

Table 13 revealed the employment status in terms of job level position most of the respondents are in Professional, technical or supervisory position with a frequency of 102 or 36.04%, 56 or 19.79 are in rank or clerical position while 44 or 15.55% of them are in management/executive position.

Job level position	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Management executive	44	15.55	4
Professional, Technical or supervisory	102	36.04	1
Rank or clerical	56	19.79	3
Self employed	33	11.66	5
No Response	48	16.96	2
Total	283	100	

Table 13: Job level position

Table 14 shows employ-ability status in terms of status of appointment of College of Agriculture graduates from before present job are Contractual with 55 or 19.43%, 43 or 15.19% are Job order status appointment, while regular appointment has 40 or 14.13%.

It implies that agriculture graduates tend to choose job under permanent status similarly with other graduates of different programs. Permanent employment acceptably mean that employees are paid time-off, have benefits such as insurance, retirement benefits, career development and advancement opportunities, sense of stability, and sense of security in having a job.

Status of Appointment	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Regular	40	14.13	5
Contractual	55	19.43	2
Job order	43	15.19	4
Probationary	37	13.07	6
Others	44	15.56	3
No response	64	22.62	1
Total	283	100	

Table 14: Employment Data in Terms of Status Appointment

C. Problem Encountered

Table 15 shows the problem encountered of graduates in looking for a job 82 or 21.52% stated that experienced no job opportunities, job is needed by special skills and their major is not related in their job with a frequency of 23 or 6.04 respectively.

The results of the current study confirm the findings of several studies that the challenge to job seekers include the lack of skills, graduates' preparation is lacking or not enough and preferences or qualifications of companies (Anderson, 2021; Porter, 2021; Kasriel, 2018; Cooper, 2018;

Pant, 2018; Campos, 2017). Since the graduates are challenged oftentimes by many factors such as the recruitment and screening process of companies or agencies, the readiness of the graduates in terms of employ-ability skills is a significant factor on the high probability of being employed. The agencies or institutions set high qualifications or standards for their applicants since they hire people who can contribute to the institution's growth and development. However, most new graduates still have dilemmas about these qualifications.

Problem encountered	Frequency	Percentage
Few job vacancies	16	4.20
Mismatch of educational qualification	5	1.32
No job opportunity	82	21.52
Job is needed special skills	23	6.04
Inadequate job experience	19	4.99
Personality factor	12	3.15
Lack of Information technology skills	8	2.10
Lack of popularity of agriculture degree	8	2.10
Lack of economic/entrepreneurial skills	12	3.15
Lack of political patronage	8	2.10
Major is not related to the job	23	6.04
Not meeting the requirements	9	2.35
Not passing the pre-employment exam	4	1.04
No Response	152	39.90

Total	381	100
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Table 15: Problem encountered of graduates in looking for a job

D. Suggestions to improve College of Agriculture Program Offering

Table 16 shows the suggestions to improve the college of agriculture program offering majority of the graduates-respondents suggested the upgrading of college facilities with a frequency of 45 or 11.81%, followed by additional faculty in soil science and agricultural economics with a frequency of 35 or 9.19% respectively, followed by providing job placement program.

It revealed that the following suggestions of the agriculture graduates which are know something about in the field of crops and animals because students can easily find a work because it will be your advantage to other applicants and they are flexible, they can give you a job related to crops or to animals more hands on practices and availability and additional equipment (for agriculture) to be used by the future students.

Suggestions	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Have a specialization (Animal/Crop)	30	7.87	6
Partnership in Government offices like ATI	13	3.41	13
Providing job placement program	33	8.66	4
Sustain the functional college facilities	12	3.15	14.5
Additional Faculty in Agricultural economics	35	9.19	2.5
Additional Faculty in Soil science	35	9.19	2.5
Upgrading of college facilities	45	11.81	1
Establish animal production facilities	23	6.04	7
Conduct review for the licensure examinations	18	4.72	10
Have strong linkages in private firm	9	2.36	16
Develop crop production facilities	12	3.15	14.5
Create a sustainable student farm	8	2.10	17
More hands-on practices	7	1.84	18
More involvement of students in research activities	21	5.51	8.5
More involvement of students in extension activities	17	4.46	11
Additional laboratory equipment's	21	5.51	8.5
Curriculum and syllabi should be reviewed	16	4.20	12
No Response	31	8.14	5
Total	381	100	

Table 16: Suggestions to improve College of Agriculture Program Offering

IV. CONCLUSION/S AND RECOMMENDATION/S

The finding of this research led to the following conclusion that there is a need to improve the employment rate of graduates from the College of Agriculture, The graduates experienced lack of job opportunities in this time of pandemic, and lack of competence in the job. This study resulted to the following recommendation it served as motivation to students to study hard and have perseverance to attain their goal to become more successful graduates, strengthen the alumni placement program, the colleges may sustain and improved facilities for the field and hands-on activities of the students and the University may consider additional faculty in the field of soil science, and agricultural economics. Scholarship program of government and other benefactors may be pursued and made available to poor but deserving students so that they could be given opportunity to continue their higher education and be able to land a better job. Further study may recommends focus on the strategies on the improvement of the Program curriculum offered by the college.

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